

Synthesis, spectral, thermal, biological and 3D molecular modeling studies of oxidomolybdenum(V) and dioxidomolybdenum(VI) complexes derived from 2,4-dihydroxyacetophenone isonicotinoylhydrazone

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Abstract : Synthesis of some novel oxidomolybdenum(V) and dioxidomolybdenum(VI) complexes with a Schiff base, (2,4-dihydroxy acetophenoneisonicotinoylhydrazone) (DAIH), derived from 2,4-dihydroxy acetophenone and isonicotinoylhydrazide are reported. The complexes have been characterized by elemental analyses, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility data, IR, UV-Vis, EPR, ¹H NMR and FAB mass spectral studies. The physico-chemical studies and spectral data indicate that the ligand (DAIH) acts as a monovalent tridentate chelating agent. The FAB mass and X-band EPR spectra indicate that the pentavalent Mo in the complex is monomeric in nature. The X-ray diffraction studies of the complex [MoO(DAIH)Cl₂] correspond to orthorhombic crystal lattice with unit cell dimensions $a = 16.64 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 13.25 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 9.56 \text{ \AA}$. All the complexes are found to be neutral with distorted octahedral geometry. The thermal behaviour of the complex [MoO(DAIH)Cl₂] was investigated by thermogravimetric techniques. The ligand (DAIH) and its two complexes [MoO(DAIH)Cl₂], [MoO₂(DAIH)Cl] were screened for their *in vitro* antibacterial activity. The complexes exhibited higher activity than the ligand (DAIH). The 3D molecular modeling and analysis for bond length and bond angles have also been carried out for one of the representative compounds, [MoO(DAIH)Cl₂].

Keywords : Isonicotinoylhydrazide, molybdenum, 3D molecular modeling.

Introduction

Molybdenum is a biologically important trace metal that occurs in the redox - active sites of molybdoenzymes involved in nitrogen, carbon or sulphur metabolism. The higher oxidation states of molybdenum are dominated by complexes that contain the oxido and dioxido molybdenum groups^{1,2}. The 'oxido-type' molybdoenzymes, which possess a common Mo cofactor, catalyze common biological two electron reactions. Molybdenum also influences protein synthesis, and the metabolism of phosphorus, potassium, iron, copper, zinc and iodine. The potential applications of molybdenum compounds are many^{3,4}. This class of compounds is interesting also in the study of problems associated with the *trans* influence of the oxygen donor atoms⁵. Recently there has been considerable interest in the chemistry of hydrazone compounds because of their potential pharmacological applications^{6,7}. In previous studies, we have synthesized certain new complexes of oxidomolybdenum(V) and dioxidomolybdenum(VI) complexes derived from isonicotinoyl-

hydrazone (INH) having anticancer and antibacterial properties¹. In order to examine further the coordination abilities and complexation behavior of hydrazone based ligands, we have extended the study on the syntheses of some oxidomolybdenum(V) and dioxidomolybdenum(VI) complexes derived from 2,4-dihydroxyacetophenoneisonicotinoylhydrazone (DAIH) (Fig. 1).

DAIH

Fig. 1

Results and discussion

The chemical analyses data and physical properties of

the ligand and their complexes are given in Table 1. All the complexes are coloured, non-hygroscopic solids and stable in air. They are sparingly soluble in common or-

value (1.73 B.M.) expected for oxidomolybdenum(V) complexes showing the absence of Mo-Mo interaction⁹. All the dioxidomolybdenum(VI) complexes are found to

Table 1. Analytical data of the ligand and its complexes

Complex	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)						μ_{eff} (B.M.)
	Mo	C	H	N	Cl	S	
DAIH	-	61.65 (61.99)	4.95 (4.83)	15.24 (15.49)	-	-	-
[MoO(DAIH)Cl ₂]	21.68 (21.17)	37.35 (37.11)	2.69 (2.67)	9.32 (9.27)	16.02 (15.65)	-	1.72
[MoO(DAIH)NCS]	20.06 (20.17)	38.81 (37.87)	2.39 (2.54)	11.83 (11.78)	7.79 (7.45)	6.47 (6.74)	1.80
[MoO(DAIH)NO ₃ Cl]	20.27 (20.00)	35.25 (35.06)	2.73 (2.52)	11.45 (11.68)	7.67 (7.39)	-	1.68
[MoO(DAIH)ClO ₄ Cl]	18.87 (18.55)	32.36 (32.52)	2.61 (2.30)	8.80 (8.13)	13.9 (13.7)	-	1.76
[MoO ₂ (DAIH)Cl]	22.26 (22.12)	38.91 (38.78)	2.83 (2.79)	9.72 (9.69)	8.54 (8.17)	-	-
[MoO ₂ (DAIH)NCS]	21.47 (21.03)	39.87 (39.48)	2.82 (2.65)	12.71 (12.28)	-	6.98 (7.03)	-
[MoO ₂ (DAIH)NO ₃]	20.64 (20.85)	36.09 (36.54)	2.53 (2.63)	12.59 (12.17)	-	-	-
[MoO ₂ (DAIH)ClO ₄]	19.97 (19.28)	34.81 (33.79)	2.58 (2.43)	8.37 (8.44)	7.29 (7.12)	-	-

ganic solvents, like ethanol, methanol and acetonitrile, insoluble in acetone, chloroform, and completely soluble in DMF and DMSO.

The molar conductance values of 10⁻³ M solutions of complexes lie in the range 40–60 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ in dry DMF indicate their non electrolyte behaviour⁸. All the oxido complexes show magnetic moment values in the range 1.68–1.80 B.M., which corresponds to spin-only

be diamagnetic as expected for a d⁰ system. The results show that the ligand coordinates to the metal ion in 1 : 1 ratio and suggest that the proposed formulae are [MoO(DAIH)ClX] and [MoO₂(DAIH)X], where X = Cl, NCS, ClO₄, NO₃.

Important infrared spectral bands of the ligand and complexes and their tentative assignments are given in Table 2. The characteristic IR signals for the ligand cor-

Table 2. IR spectral data of DAIH and its complexes

Ligand/Complexes	$\nu_{\text{O-H}}$	$\nu_{\text{N-H}}$	$\nu_{\text{C=O}}$	$\nu_{\text{C=N}}$	$\delta_{\text{O-H}}$	$\nu_{\text{C-O}}$	$\nu_{\text{N-N}}$	$\nu_{\text{M=O (sym)}}$	$\nu_{\text{M=O (asym)}}$
DAIH	3070	3258	1655	1633	1373	1298	999	-	-
[MoO(DAIH)Cl ₂]	3414	3260	1634	1610	1374	1298	1025	932	-
[MoO(DAIH)NCS]	3495	3259	1633	1611	1375	1296	1021	936	-
[MoO(DAIH)NO ₃ Cl]	3393	3252	1630	1609	1375	1297	1018	943	-
[MoO(DAIH)ClO ₄ Cl]	3450	3255	1640	1609	1370	1299	1010	936	-
[MoO ₂ (DAIH)Cl]	3520	3253	1637	1614	1377	1290	1009	930	904
[MoO ₂ (DAIH)NCS]	3395	3258	1639	1612	1379	1297	1023	929	905
[MoO ₂ (DAIH)NO ₃]	3475	3259	1635	1618	1376	1297	1012	935	902
[MoO ₂ (DAIH)ClO ₄]	3400	3252	1638	1617	1374	1298	1014	930	904

responding to (i) OH; (ii) NH; (iii) C=O; (iv) C=N; (v) C–O were analyzed. An absorption band occurring at 3258 cm⁻¹ in the free ligand can be assigned to the $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ stretching vibration¹⁰. In the complexes, this band remains unaltered. This suggests non-participation of the NH group in bonding. There is a strong and very broad band centered around 3070 cm⁻¹, which is characteristic of strong hydrogen bonded O–H vibration in the Schiff base ligand¹¹. The ligand spectrum display two bands at 1373 and 1327 cm⁻¹ (OH-deformation) and two bands at 1298 and 1282 cm⁻¹ (phenolic C–O). This doublet peak is due to the presence of two phenolic (OH) substituents in the phenyl ring¹². In the infrared spectra of complexes, the broad band centered at 3070 cm⁻¹ disappears and another sharp band appear around 3400 cm⁻¹.

Evidently, the hydrogen bond is broken during complexation. The OH group taking part in hydrogen bonding is likely to be the one adjacent to the azomethine group (position 2) and the free OH group in position 4. This is supported by the fact that on complexation, the band at 1327 cm⁻¹ disappeared while the band at 1373 cm⁻¹ still exist. On the other hand, one of the two $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ of phenol (1298 cm⁻¹) appears nearly in its position as for the ligand, whereas the other shifts¹³ to higher frequency, (from 1282 to ~1309 cm⁻¹). This behaviour indicates that DAIH behaves as monobasic tridentate ligand and has free OH in the *para* position. The $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ (1655 cm⁻¹) and $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ (1633 cm⁻¹) bands in the spectrum of ligand show downward shift by ~25 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the complexes indicating coordination through carbonyl oxygen¹⁴ and azomethine nitrogen¹³ respectively. The coordination through the azomethine nitrogen atom is further supported by the shift of $\nu_{\text{N-N}}$ vibration, observed at 999 cm⁻¹ in the ligand, to higher frequency by ~26 cm⁻¹ in the complexes. It is due to the reduction of lone pair repulsive forces in the adjacent nitrogen atoms¹⁵.

Dioxidomolybdenum(VI) complexes display two Mo=O stretches at ~930 cm⁻¹ and ~900 cm⁻¹ due to symmetric and antisymmetric stretching of *cis*-MoO₂²⁺ core¹⁶. The MoO₂²⁺ prefers to form a *cis* configuration due to maximum utilization of the *d* π groups. A very strong band observed ~935 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of oxidomolybdenum(V) complexes corresponds to Mo=O stretching frequency. The new weak bands ~550 cm⁻¹ and ~460 cm⁻¹ in the metal complexes have been as-

signed to $\nu_{\text{Mo-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Mo-N}}$, modes respectively¹⁷.

The IR spectra of the nitrate complexes are suggestive of monocoordinated nitrate group (ν_4 ~1530 cm⁻¹, ν_1 ~1380 cm⁻¹ and ν_2 ~1034 cm⁻¹). Two split bands observed ~1130 cm⁻¹ and ~1058 cm⁻¹ assigned to (ν_4) and (ν_1) and another set of split bands, ~640 cm⁻¹ and ~610 cm⁻¹, assigned to ν_3 and ν_5 vibrations, are characteristic of monodentately coordinated perchlorate group¹⁸. This is supported by the molar conductance data. The N-coordinated nature of the thiocyanate group is indicated by the $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ (~2060 cm⁻¹), $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ (~800 cm⁻¹), δ_{NCS} (~470 cm⁻¹) bands.

The ¹H NMR spectrum of the Schiff base ligand in DMSO-*d*₆ shows slightly broad and medium resonance peak at 13.39, 12.61, 10.09 and 9.94 ppm due to 2-OH and 4-OH protons¹⁹. The NH signal is observed as another singlet at 11.41 ppm. It indicates that the ligand exists in the keto form. In the high field region -CH₃ proton appears as sharp and singlet peaks at 2.41 ppm. The aromatic protons appear as multiplets within the range δ (8.69–8.78) (isonicotinic 4H) and δ (6.2–7.8) (phenyl 3H) for the ligand. The sharp signal found as a singlet at δ (2.51) may be due to the water present in DMSO-*d*₆ sample used¹⁰.

The electronic spectra of the ligand DAIH in methanol showed two absorption maxima at 268 nm ($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$) and 314 nm ($n \rightarrow \pi^*$). The UV absorption spectra of all oxido complexes showed a red shift to ~275 nm and ~325 nm, indicating the coordination of DAIH with molybdenum (Table 3). The complexes exhibit three bands in the region ~380 nm, ~490 nm and ~680–760 nm

Table 3. Electronic absorptions of DAIH and its oxido complexes

Ligand/complex	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$	$n \rightarrow \pi^*$	LMCT	<i>d-d</i>
DAIH	268	314	-	-
[MoO(DAIH)Cl ₂]	279	325	360	382, 490, 680
[MoO(DAIH)ClNCS]	275	327	358	376, 483, 762
[MoO(DAIH)NO ₃ Cl]	290	346	365	388, 494, 695
[MoO(DAIH)ClO ₄ Cl]	274	330	363	386, 496, 705

assigned to ²B₂ → ²A₁ (*d*_{xy} → *d*_{z²}), ²B₂ → ²B₁ (*d*_{xy} → *d*_{x²-y²}) and ²B₂ → ²E (*d*_{xy} → *d*_{xz}, *d*_{yz}) transitions respectively (the unpaired electron is in the *d*_{xy} orbital)^{20,21}. The electronic spectra indicate octahedral environment for all the complexes and are in conformity with the

Ballhausen-Gray scheme for an octahedral structure²¹. The complexes are best considered as octahedral with strong tetragonal distortion, resulting from Mo=O bond.

In the FAB mass spectrum of ligand (DAIH) characteristic groups of the peaks are found to be centered around mass numbers corresponding to the molecular ion $(M+1)^+$, $(M-15)^+$, $(M-58)^+$, $(M-74)^+$, $(M-93)^+$, $(M-106)^+$, $(M-148)^+$ etc. The molecular ion peak is also the base peak. Mass spectrum of its oxido complex was also recorded and their stoichiometric composition compared. The molecular ion peak for the ligand is at 272.27 ($C_{14}H_{13}N_3O_3$), whereas its complex shows the molecular

The X-ray powder diffraction patterns of the complex $[MoO(DAIH)Cl_2]$ were indexed (Fig. 2). Table 4 for orthorhombic system using Heuss and Lipson's procedure^{24,25}. The lattice constants are $A = 0.002141$, $B = 0.003377$ and $C = 0.006486$ and hence the unit cell dimensions calculated were $a = 16.64 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 13.25 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 9.56 \text{ \AA}$.

Thermal behaviour of the complex $[MoO(DAIH)Cl_2]$ was studied by TGA in air at a heating rate of $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ per min in conjunction with DTG and DTA (Fig. 3). The stability range extend from ambient temperature to $170 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The initial mass loss of 1-2% may be due to the desorp-

Fig. 2. X-Ray diffraction patterns of $[MoO(DAIH)Cl_2]$.

ion peak at 453.62 $[MoO(C_{14}H_{12}N_3O_3)Cl_2]$ which confirms the stoichiometry of the oxido complex as $[MoO(DAIH)Cl_2]$. Presence of peaks at $m/z = 418.59$ $[M-Cl]^+$ and 383.27 $[M-Cl-Cl]^+$ in the complex suggests the presence of two chloride ions in the complex²².

The X-band EPR spectrum of $[MoO(DAIH)Cl_2]$ recorded in the polycrystalline form at room temperature. The spectrum obtained at a microwave frequency 9.40 GHz and field strength of 3200 G exhibits a single line only which is characteristic of monomeric oxidomolybdenum(V) complexes. The EPR parameters²³ were found to be $g_{\parallel} = 1.9853$, $g_{\perp} = 1.9651$ and $g_{av} = 1.9718$.

Table 4. XRD data of $[MoO(DAIH)Cl_2]$

Line	$\sin^2\theta$ (obs)	$\sin^2\theta$ (cal)	hkl	Intensity
1	0.00988	0.009883	011	75.43
2	0.011937	0.011941	210	100.00
3	0.022519	0.022646	310	32.16
4	0.028616	0.028558	221	31.35
5	0.030872	0.030393	030	29.58
6	0.037911	0.037885	212	42.29
7	0.041607	0.041593	122	48.89
8	0.044665	0.044119	411	27.20
10	0.082092	0.082117	142	7.74

Fig. 3 TG, DTG and DTA curves of $[\text{MoO}(\text{DAIH})\text{Cl}_2]$.

tion of moisture. The decomposition of the complex takes place in three stages. First stage of decomposition starts at 170 °C and it completes at 230 °C. The observed endothermic DTA peak with a maximum at 210 °C having a mass loss of 7.6% (7.8% calc) is assigned to the elimination of one chlorine atom. Second stage of decomposition is complicated as is evident from the exothermic peak at 297 °C and 339 °C. It ranges from 290 °C to 400 °C. The weight loss at this stage is 42.5% and this stage could not be assigned to any specific decomposition. After this stage, weight loss takes place slowly and continuously. The sample showed another weight loss in the region 680–790 °C. The weight of the sample at 780 °C was less than that may be expected if MoO_3 was formed. This may be due to the volatilization²⁶ of MoO_3 above 770 °C.

The kinetic and thermodynamic parameters were calculated using Coats-Redfern equation (Table 5). The val-

Table 5. Kinetic parameters for the two stages of thermal decomposition of $[\text{MoO}(\text{DAIH})\text{Cl}_2]$

Stage	Peak temp. (K)	Activation energy (E) (kJ mol^{-1})	Pre-exponential factor (A) (s^{-1})	Entropy of activation (ΔS) ($\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$)
I	483	145.94	7.53×10^{13}	16.74
II	607	121.47	1.0191×10^8	-97.51

ues of $\ln g(\alpha)/T^2$ versus $1/T \times 10^3$ plots were linear (Figs. 4a, 4b). The fitness was tested by evaluating the correlation coefficient (Tables 6a and 6b). The values of activation energy (E) were obtained from the slope and that of pre-exponential factor (A) from the intercept of the straight line. The entropy of activation (ΔS) was also estimated.

The pathogenic bacterial microorganisms viz. *Salmonella typhi* MTCC 734, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* MTCC 2642, *Escherichia coli* 585, *Proteus vulgaris* 177, *Bacillus subtilis* 2248 and *Streptococcus thermophilus* 1938

Fig. 4a. Coats-Redfern plot for stage I decomposition of $[\text{MoO}(\text{DAIH})\text{Cl}_2]$.

Fig. 4b. Coats-Redfern plot for stage II decomposition of [MoO(DAIH)Cl₂].

ligands. Increased activity of metal chelate can be explained on the basis of the overtone concept and chelation theory. According to the Overtone's concept of cell permeability, the lipid membrane that surrounds the cell favors the passage of only lipid-soluble materials due to which liposolubility is an important factor which controls the antimicrobial activity. On chelation, the polarity of the metal ion will be reduced to a greater extent due to overlap of ligand orbital and partial sharing of the positive charge of the metal ion with donor groups. Further it increases the delocalization of π -electrons over the whole chelate ring and enhances the lipophilicity of complexes²⁷. This increased lipophilicity enhances the penetration of complexes into the lipid membranes and blocks the metal binding sites in enzymes of microorganisms. These complexes also disturb the respiration process of the cell and

Table 6a. Computational details for the stage I decomposition of [MoO(DAIH)Cl₂]

T (°C)	mg	n = 1		W	r = 0.99889		CR
		T (K)	RT		α	g(α)	
170	3.56	443	2.25734	0	0	0	-
180	3.54	453	2.20751	0.02	0.07407	0.07696	-14.79624
190	3.51	463	2.15983	0.05	0.18519	0.20479	-13.8612
200	3.47	473	2.11416	0.09	0.33333	0.40547	-13.22091
210	3.39	483	2.07039	0.17	0.62963	0.99325	-12.3668
220	3.32	493	2.0284	0.24	0.88889	2.19722	-11.61382
230	3.29	503	1.98807	0.27	1	-	-

Table 6b. Computational details for the stage II decomposition of [MoO(DAIH)Cl₂]

T (°C)	mg	n = 1.2		W	r = 0.99354		CR
		T (K)	RT		α	g(α)	
310	2.92	583	1.71527	0.19	0.14729	0.1619	-14.55716
320	2.8	593	1.68634	0.31	0.24031	0.28254	-14.03433
330	2.63	603	1.65837	0.48	0.37209	0.48771	-13.52187
340	2.43	613	1.63132	0.68	0.52713	0.80794	-13.05
350	2.26	623	1.60514	0.85	0.65891	1.20008	-12.6867
360	2.13	633	1.57978	0.98	0.75969	1.64991	-12.40022
370	2.03	643	1.55521	1.08	0.83721	2.1886	-12.14903
380	1.94	653	1.53139	1.17	0.90698	3.03992	-11.85132

$$CR = \ln \frac{g(\alpha)}{T_2}, RT = \frac{1 \times 10^2}{T(K)}$$

were selected for the antibacterial screening and the results were presented in Table 7.

The antibacterial studies reveal that metal complexes exhibit higher antibacterial activity than uncomplexed

thus block the synthesis of proteins, which restricts further growth of the organism.

The molecular modeling of the proposed configuration (Fig. 5) of [MoO(DAIH)Cl₂], as a representative,

Table 7. Antibacterial activity of DAIH and its complexes against pathogenic bacteria

Ligand/Complex	Zone of inhibition in mm dia.					
	<i>S. typhi</i> MTCC 734	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> MTCC 2642	<i>E. coli</i> MTCC 585	<i>Proteus vulgaris</i> 1771	<i>B. subtilis</i> 2248	<i>S. thermophilus</i> 1938
[MoO ₂ (DAIH)Cl]	-	14	-	-	T	-
[MoO(DAIH)Cl ₂]	-	-	-	T	T	-
DAIH	-	-	-	-	-	T
Control (Chloroform at 10 µl/disc)	-	-	-	-	-	-

- = No activity; T = Trace (<8 mm).

Fig. 5 Proposed 3D molecular structure of [MoO(DAIH)Cl₂].

was constructed using Modeling and Analysis²⁸ software CHEM 3D, Pro version 7.0.0. The actual bond length/bond angles are calculated values as a result of energy minimization in CHEM 3D, while the optimal bond length/optimal bond angle values are the most desirable/favorable (standard) bond length/bond angles established by the builder unit of the CHEM 3D. In all, 112 measurements of the bond length (39 in numbers), plus the bond angles (73 in numbers) are obtained. In most cases, the actual bond length and bond angles are close to the optimal values, and thus the proposed structure of the compound as well as the others are acceptable²⁹. Selected actual bond length/bond angle around the octahedral surrounding is given in Table 8. Due to the limitation of the software, optimal bond length/optimal bond angle around the octahedral surrounding could not be generated³⁰. Proposed 3D structures of DAIH and [MoO₂(DAIH)Cl] are given in Figs. 6 and 7.

Table 8 Selected bond lengths/bond angles of complex [MoO(DAIH)Cl₂]

Atoms	Actual bond length, Å	Atoms	Actual bond angle, deg.
Mo(20)-O(8)	1.971	O(8)-Mo(20)-N(11)	84.484
Mo(20)-N(11)	1.928	O(8)-Mo(20)-O(19)	164.587
Mo(20)-O(22)	1.699	O(8)-Mo(20)-Cl(21)	83.167
Mo(20)-O(19)	2.012	O(8)-Mo(20)-O(22)	88.545
Mo(20)-Cl(23)	2.313	O(8)-Mo(20)-Cl(23)	94.081
Mo(20)-Cl(21)	2.040	N(11)-Mo(20)-O(19)	83.109
		N(11)-Mo(20)-Cl(21)	167.406
		N(11)-Mo(20)-O(22)	89.477
		N(11)-Mo(20)-Cl(23)	87.795
		O(19)-Mo(20)-Cl(21)	109.477
		O(19)-Mo(20)-O(22)	82.246
		O(19)-Mo(20)-Cl(23)	94.538
		Cl(21)-Mo(20)-O(22)	92.674
		O(22)-Mo(20)-Cl(23)	176.021

Fig. 6 Proposed 3D molecular structure of DAIH

Fig. 7. Proposed 3D molecular structure of $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{DAIH})\text{Cl}]$.

On the basis of all the above spectral data and physicochemical studies, a distorted octahedral geometry (Figs. 8 and 9) is tentatively proposed for the complexes.

Experimental

Molybdenum pentachloride (Aldrich Chemicals, USA) and molybdenum trioxide (Loba Chemie, Mumbai, India) were used. All other chemicals were of AR grade.

Synthesis of ligand :

The Schiff base, DAIH ($\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3$) was prepared by mixing equimolar solutions of 2,4-dihydroxyacetophenone and isonicotinoylhydrazide in methanol and refluxing the mixture for ~4 h. The yellow solid separated on cooling was filtered, washed with methanol and dried. Purity of the ligand was monitored by TLC. It was characterized by elemental analysis, IR, UV, FAB mass

(X = Cl, NCS, NO₃, ClO₄)

Fig. 8. Proposed 2D structure of [MoO₂(DAIH)X].

(X = Cl, NCS, NO₃, ClO₄)

Fig. 9. Proposed 2D structure of [MoO(DAIH)ClX].

and NMR spectra.

Synthesis of oxidomolybdenum(V) complexes :

The chloride complex was prepared by adding a methanolic solution of MoCl₅ (20 cm³, 2 mmol) in small quantities with stirring to a hot methanolic solution of the ligand (20 cm³, 2 mmol) in methanol. The pH of the mixture was adjusted to ~4 with NaOAc/HOAc buffer and refluxed for ~2 h. The solid complex separated was suction filtered, washed with aqueous methanol, finally with ether and dried over P₄O₁₀ *in vacuo*.

The following general method was adopted for the preparation of thiocyanate, nitrate, and perchlorate complexes³¹. A methanolic solution of MoCl₅ (20 cm³, 2 mmol) containing ~0.3 g of NH₄CNS/~0.3 g LiNO₃/1-2 drops of perchloric acid as the case may be, was added to a hot methanolic solution of the ligand (20 cm³, 2 mmol). The pH of the mixture was adjusted to ~4 with NaOAc/HOAc buffer. All complexes, except the thiocyanate complex, were precipitated on refluxing the solution for ~2-3 h. The thiocyanate complex was precipitated on stirring the solution at 40 °C for ~2 h. The precipitated complex was suction filtered, washed with aqueous methanol (1 : 1) followed by dry ether and dried over P₄O₁₀ *in vacuo*.

Synthesis of dioxidomolybdenum(VI) complexes :

Dioxidocomplexes, except thiocyanate complex, were prepared by adopting following general method. A hot solution of the ligand in methanol (20 cm³, 2 mmol) was added with stirring to a hot methanolic solution of bis(acetylacetonato)-*cis* dioxidomolybdenum(VI) (20 cm³, 2 mmol) containing ~1-2 drops of conc. HCl/~0.3 g LiNO₃/1-2 drops of perchloric acid. The pH of the mix-

ture was adjusted to ~6 with NaOAc/HOAc buffer. The stirring was continued while heating (50-60 °C) for 30 min. The precipitated complexes were filtered under suction, washed with aqueous methanol, then with ether and dried in vacuum over P₄O₁₀. Thiocyanate complex was prepared from MoO₃ according to reported procedure³².

Metal, chloride and perchlorate were estimated by standard methods³³. The elemental analyses (C, H, N and S) were carried out at the Sophisticated Test and Instrumentation Center (STIC), Kochi. The IR spectra of ligand and complexes were recorded in the region 4000-400 cm⁻¹ on Perkin-Elmer 397 spectrophotometer. Room temperature molar conductance of the complexes in DMF was recorded on Elico direct reading conductivity meter at a concentration of ~10⁻³ M. Electronic absorption spectral measurements of the complexes in methanol were measured using Jasco-V-550-UV-Vis spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra of the ligand and the complexes were recorded on a 300 MHz FT NMR instrument using TMS as reference. Thermal analysis of the complex [MoO(DAIH)Cl₂] was carried out by heating in air at a rate of 10 °C per minute on a Mettler Toledo simultaneous TG-DTA system. X-Ray powder diffraction pattern was recorded using Philips X-ray PW1710 diffractometer. The FAB mass spectrum of [MoO(DAIH)Cl₂] was recorded in a JEOL JMS600H mass spectrometer. The X-Q band EPR spectrum was recorded at room temperature on Varian E-112 spectrophotometer with DPPH as the standard, from RSIC, Chennai. The magnetic susceptibilities were recorded at room temperature by Gouy method. Diamagnetic corrections for vari-

ous atoms and structural units were computed using Pascal's constants³⁴. The Temperature Independent Paramagnetism (TIP) for Mo⁵⁺, 55 × 10⁻⁶ CGS units were also incorporated.

The ligand (DAIH) and its two complexes [MoO(DAIH)Cl₂] and [MoO₂(DAIH)Cl] were screened *in vitro* for their possible antibacterial activities against *S. typhi* MTCC 734, *P. aeruginosa* MTCC 2642, *E. coli* 585, *P. vulgaris* 177, *B. subtilis* 2248 and *S. thermophilus* 1938 using the disc diffusion method³⁵ (Kirby Bauer Method).

All the plates were allowed to air dry in sterile conditions and swabbed with the pure culture of bacteria on the MHA plates. Already prepared sterile discs impregnated with the compounds of the study were placed above the seeded plates aseptically with a sterile forceps. A disc was also used except any compound but only chloroform to maintain the control. The plates were incubated for 24 h at 37 °C and the zone of inhibition of the antibiotic compound against the bacteria can be measured by measuring the zones of inhibition around the bacterial cultures and was measured by the diameter of the zone in millimeters.

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